

Account of Obligations in Budget Organizations Improvement

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Abstract:

The state budget budget policy in various stages of economic development implementation tool, implementation of planned programs and activities is the main source of funds. Use of budget funds State financial control over the financial stability of these conditions represents the state financial policy aimed at creation.

Keywords: Accounting and management, Financial Reporting, ACCA calculation.

Preparation of accounting and financial reporting in the Republic of Uzbekistan improvement of the process on a global scale, in the developed countries of the world best practices in the field of accounting and auditing, as well as Financial Reporting

It requires the study and implementation of International Standards. Business entities involved in the development and growth of our country's economy it is important to reduce the amount of liabilities. Business entities obligations directly affect their financial status and solvency. That's it due to this, it is important to determine their level and to comply with the repayment terms is counted.

Accounting and management of public sector assets and liabilities worldwide is attracting more and more attention. Even the cost of our various public services higher than our neighbors. International Federation of Accountants in 2004 national, for the public sector for regional, local government bodies and relevant agencies issued international accounting standards (IPSAS). in the UK and elsewhere In developed countries, this organization prepares financial statements, balance sheets and other reports they prepare. Tax revenues to increase public assets worldwide there are reproduction fees, but our tax revenue is the lowest in the world is one of the indicators. Privatization and the deficit of the state and the economy reform of loss-making enterprises to reduce the liabilities of their subjects is one of the urgent problems. The textbook, monograph and

textbooks, as well as obligations in published scientific articles and theses theoretical problems of accounting and auditing are partially studied. For example, V.V. Kovalev according to the rule, "in the legal sense, debtor and creditor debts in the financial statement is an example of obligations that represent legal civil relations. Nowadays, it is the first thing to study the calculation of liabilities in budget organizations it is necessary to study their characteristics.

Obligations have three main characteristics:

- the event giving rise to the obligation must be reasonable;
- obligations to another subject only transfer of assets or provision of services
- can be satisfied by;
- obligations should not cause controversy.

When there is an obligation arising from an event that took place in ACCA requires recognition of provisions on termination of use and in the contract restoration of the specified property or other long-term asset at the expense of future expenses is likely to be implemented. ACCA requires the recording of the obligation, even with the established form of implementation of planned or similar activities even if there is a constructive obligation. In addition, according to ACCA calculation of the obligation differs in several respects, characteristic for the obligation using the current discount rate and interest expense on the income statement is included in the discount. When an obligation is accepted according to the given definition, it is recognized immediately and should be included in the accounting records.

Determination of financial obligations and their separate composition in the financial report for expression, they are classified according to at least three criteria:

1. Return the amount due to the creditor on the legal basis existence or absence of legal rights to receive;
2. Depending on the level of conditionality, i.e. when uncertain future events occur depending on the origin, size and duration of obligations;
3. By form or type.

For the first criterion, the following cases should be noted:

- A. Legal (legal) obligations, from concluding a contract, laws and various arising from treatments;
- B. Due to direct obligations, established business practice and other reasons taken voluntarily.
- C. Legal and binding obligations, the business transaction is binding, agreed and one resulting from the consolidation of bilateral obligations.

With the types of obligations in the regulatory documents in force in our republic

The following are the types of obligations used in international standards or practice shown in the table.

Based on today's practice of accounting, from among buyers some of them are dissatisfied with their purchase and want to get their money back comes out. Accordingly, in the amount of the best-estimated amount of refunds reservation is required.

In the recognition of reserves, as evidence of the inevitability of payment of liabilities attention should be paid. It is the lack of this evidence in the following cases does not allow the creation of a reserve related to expenses:

- the existence of a simple desire to carry out these expenses;
- Expectation of future operating expenses;

- expected impairment of assets

In conclusion Produced by economic entities in the current economic conditions

if he sells his product on the basis of advance payment without lending it on the condition of purchase or in front of the state budget if he collects payments for the products sold on time obligations, wages and incentive money for workers and employees provides an opportunity for timely execution, which forms a stable economic system.

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